

ISic3544

I.Sicily inscription 3544

Language

Ancient Greek and Punic

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

base

and dedication

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Valletta, Malta, National Museum of
Archaeology

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140927

1. Ĺ DNN LMLQRT B̄ L ŠR 'Š NDR

2. 'BDK 'BĐ SR W̄ H̄Y 'SRŠMR

3. ŠN BN 'SRŠMR BN 'BĐ SR K ŠM̄

4. QLM YBRKM

5.

6. Domino nostro Melqarto domino Tyri, quod voverunt

7. servi tui Abdosir et frater eius Osiršamar,

8. ambo filii Osiršamari, filii Abdosiri, quia audiit

9. vocem eorum; benedicat eis.

10.

11. Διονύσιος καὶ Σαραπίων οἱ

12. Σαραπίωνος Τύριοι

13. Ἡρακλεῖ ἀρχηγέτει.

14.

15. Ĺ DNN LMLQRT B̄ L ŠR 'Š NDR 'BDK

16. 'BÐ SR W̄.....HY 'SRŠMR ŠN BN
17. 'SRŠMR BN 'BÐ SR K ŠM̄ QLM
18. YBRKM
- 19.
20. Domino nostro Melqarto domino Tyri, quod voverunt servi tui
21. Abdosir et frater eius Osiršamar, ambo filii
22. Osiršamari, filii Abdosiri, quia audiit vocem eorum;
23. benedicat eis.
- 24.
25. Διονύσιος καὶ Σαραπίων οἱ
26. Σαραπίωνος Τύριοι Ἡρακλεῖ
27. ἀρχηγέτει.
- 28.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

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